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DATA MINING CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS FOR KIDNEY DISEASE PREDICTION

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ABSTRACT

Data mining is a non-trivial process of categorizing valid, novel, potentially useful and ultimately understandable patterns in data. In terms, it accurately state as the extraction of information from a huge database. Data mining is a vital role in several applications such as business organizations, educational institutions, government sectors, health care industry, scientific and engineering. . In the health care industry, the data mining is predominantly used for disease prediction. Enormous data mining techniques are existing for predicting diseases namely classification, clustering, association rules, summarizations, regression and etc. The main objective of this research work is to predict kidney diseases using classification algorithms such as Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machine. This research work mainly focused on finding the best classification algorithm based on the classification accuracy and execution time performance factors. From the experimental results it is observed that the performance of the SVM is better than the Naive Bayes classifier algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, Disease prediction, SVM, Naïve Bayes, Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR)

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REFERENCE

[1] AndrewKusiak, Bradley Dixonb, Shital Shaha, (2005) [Predicting survival time for kidney dialysis patients: a data mining approach](#), Elsevier Publication, Computers in Biology and Medicine 35, page no 311–327

[2] Anu Chaudhary, Puneet Garg,(2014) [Detecting and Diagnosing a Disease by Patient Monitoring System](#), International Journal of Mechanical Engineering And Information Technology, Vol. 2 Issue 6 //June //Page No: 493-499.

[3] Approaches, Knowledge-Oriented Applications in Data Mining, Prof. Kimito Funatsu (Ed.), ISBN: 978-953-307-154-1, InTech, <http://www.intechopen.com/books/knowledge-oriented-applications-indatamining/mining-enrollment-data-using-descriptive-and-predictive-approaches>

[4] Cristóbal Romero, Data Mining Algorithms to Classify Students, <http://sci2s.ugr.es/keel/pdf/specific/congreso/Data%20Mining%20Algorithms%20to%20Classify%20>

[Students.pdf](#)

- [5] Fadzilah Siraj, Mansour Ali Abdoulha, (2011). [Mining Enrollment Data Using Descriptive and Predictive](#)
- [6] [George Dimitoglou, Comparison of the C4.5 and a Naive Bayes Classifier for the Prediction of Lung Cancer Survivability](#)
- [7] Giovanni Caocci, Roberto Baccoli, Roberto Littera, Sandro Orrù, Carlo Carcassi and Giorgio La Nasa, Comparison Between an Artificial Neural Network and Logistic Regression in Predicting Long Term Kidney Transplantation Outcome, Chapter 5, an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/53104>
- [8] Gualtieri. J. A, Chettri. S. R, Crompton. R. F and Johnson.L. F, (1999) [Support vector machine classifiers as applied to AVIRIS data](#), in Summaries 8th JPL Airborne Earth Science Workshop, JPL Pub. 99-17, pp. 217–227.
- [9] Ian H. Witten and Eibe Frank.(2005) [Data Mining: Practical machine learning tools and techniques](#). Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA, 2nd edition
- [10] Lakshmi. K.R, Nagesh. Y and VeeraKrishna. M, (2014) [Performance Comparison Of Three Data Mining Techniques For Predicting Kidney Dialysis Survivability](#), International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Technology, Mar., Vol. 7, Issue 1, pg no. 242-254.
- [11] Mahesh Mudhol Purushothama Gowda,(2004) [Data Mining in the Process of Knowledge Discovery in Digital Libraries](#), 2nd Convention PLANNER, Manipur Uni., Imphal, 4-5 November, 2004, page no 164-167
- [12] Ruben D. Canlas Jr,(2009) [Data Mining In Healthcare: Current Applications And Issues](#), August
- [13] Tadjudin. S and Landgrebe. D.A, (1999) [Covariance estimation with limited training samples](#), IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote. Sensing, vol. 37, pp. 2113–2118, July
- [14] Tommaso Di Noia, Vito Claudio Ostuni, Francesco Pesce, Giulio Binetti, David Naso, Francesco Paolo Schena, Eugenio Di Sciascio,(2013) [An end stage kidney disease predictor based on an artificial neural networks ensemble](#), Elsevier Publication, Expert Systems with Applications 40, page no 4438–4445
- [15] Uffe B. Kjærulff, Anders L. Madsen, (2005) [Probabilistic Networks — an Introduction to Bayesian Networks and Influence Diagrams](#), 10 May
- [16] Vijayarani. S, Sudha. S, (2013) [Comparative Analysis of Classification Function Techniques for Heart Disease Prediction](#), International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 1, Issue 3, May, page no 735- 741
- [17] Zhang H.; Su J, Naive Bayesian classifiers for ranking. Paper appeared in ECML2004 15th European Conference on Machine Learning, Pisa, Italy.

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